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Мазкур журнал 6 та халқаро маълумотлар базаларида индексланган бўлиб, жорий йил учун **UIF 2023 = 7.5 “импакт-фактор”** кўрсаткичига эга.

Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий таълим, фан ва инновациялар вазирлиги ҳузуридаги Олий аттестация комиссиясининг 2023 йил 24 июлдаги 01-02/1199-сонли хатига мувофиқ ушбу журналда чоп этилган мақолалар **хорижий мақолалар сифатида тан олинади.**

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ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

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LEGAL BASIS FOR COMBATING DRUG CRIME IN GERMANY

ANNOTATION

The article examines the problems associated with drug crime in Germany. The law on drug trafficking of July 28, 1981 is analyzed, and statistical data on crimes in the field of illicit drug trafficking is provided. The scientific novelty of the study is determined by a systematic analysis of the features of the German national strategy in the field of combating drug trafficking. The information obtained as a result of the study is also novel, and is of interest for the further development of scientific research and improvement of the fight against drug addiction.

Key words: World Health Organization, drugs, drug crime, crime prevention, drug trafficking, drug addiction, minors, criminal legal measures, legalization, government control.

Германияда гиёҳвандликка қарши курашишнинг ҳуқуқий асослари

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада Германияда гиёҳвандлик воситалар жинояти билан боғлиқ муаммолар кўриб чиқилган. 1981 йил 28 июлдаги “Гиёҳванд моддаларнинг ноқонуний айланиши тўғрисидаги қонун таҳлил қилиниб, гиёҳқандлик воситаларининг ноқонуний айланиши соҳасидаги жиноятлар тўғрисидаги статистик маълумотлар келтирилган. Тадқиқотнинг илмий янгилиги гиёҳвандлик воситаларнинг ноқонуний айланишига қарши курашиш соҳасидаги Германия миллий стратегиясининг хусусиятларини тизимли таҳлил қилиш билан белгиланади. Тадқиқот натижасида олинган маълумотлар ҳам янги бўлиб, илмий тадқиқотларни янада ривожлантириш ва гиёҳвандликка қарши курашни такомиллаштириш учун қизиқиш уйғотади.

Калит сўзлар: Жаҳон соғлиқни сақлаш ташкилоти, наркотиклар, гиёҳвандлик воситаларининг ноқонуний айланиши, жиноятчиликнинг олдини олиш, гиёҳванд моддалар савдоси, вояга етмаганлар, жиноий-ҳуқуқий чоралар, қонунийлаштириш, давлат назорати.

ПРАВОВАЯ ОСНОВА БОРЬБЫ С НАРКОПРЕСТУПНОСТЬЮ В ГЕРМАНИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматриваются проблемы, связанные с наркопреступностью в Германии. Проводится анализ закон об обороте наркотических средств от 28 июля 1981 г., предоставляются статистические данные по преступлениям в сфере незаконного оборота наркотических средств. Научная новизна исследования определяется системным анализом особенностей национальной стратегии Германии в сфере противодействия незаконному обороту наркотиков. Новизной отличается также и полученная в результате исследования информация, представляющая интерес для дальнейшего развития научных изысканий и совершенствования противодействия наркомании.

Ключевые слова: Всемирная организация здравоохранения, наркотики, наркопреступность, предупреждение преступности, незаконный оборот наркотиков, наркозависимость, несовершеннолетние, уголовно-правовые меры борьбы, легализация, государственный контроль.

In modern conditions, drug trafficking has become so widespread that most of the states that make up the world community are involved in it. The problem of drug addiction is growing, becoming transnational and requires concerted efforts of all states to combat it.

Analysis of the state of drug crime in a number of states allows us to highlight the features of the legislative solution to the fight against drug addiction and narcotism in "... the countries of the Near (Republic of Belarus, Tajikistan, Kazakhstan, Armenia, etc.) and Far (USA, Canada, Germany, France, China, etc. . d.) abroad, which are related to the national characteristics of the legal system of the state, the presence of international legal obligations at the level of interstate relations..." [1] and depending on whether the state is an exporter, importer or transit country of narcotic drugs.

Statistics from the World Health Organization presented in September 2014 once again confirm the danger of the drug addiction problem in the world.

According to the latest information, out of the total population of the planet, which is 7 billion people, 210 million use drugs, i.e. 3% of people on the planet are drug addicts. Minors turned out to be the most unprotected and psychologically helpless in the face of drug addiction in society.

Life difficulties, problems and the lack of life experience and skills for overcoming stressful situations in most of them, allowing them to preserve individuality and create a healthy lifestyle, self-withdrawal of parents and teachers, insufficient attention to the child's problems) lead to a sharp increase in the abuse of alcohol-containing products and stimulants, as well as drugs.

In addition, the insufficient level of development of states, institutions and traditions of society, political passivity and legal incompetence of the population of a number of states are factors constraining national development and threatening national security.

All this necessitates the development of a state policy regarding education aimed at fostering democratic citizenship and developing legal literacy among minors [2].

The internal system of a certain state has its own socio-historical characteristics and expresses the policy of this state, which reflects the attitude towards the problems of crime, including those related to drug addiction and the involvement of minors in illicit drug trafficking.

Realizing the multifaceted nature of the public danger, as well as the scale of various negative consequences of negative social phenomena associated with the spread of drugs, the world community began to take measures to counteract it.

A number of well-known international documents were adopted: the Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs (1961), the Convention on Psychotropic Substances (1971), the UN Convention against Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances (1988).

The states that have signed and ratified these Conventions have built and continue to build their future foreign and domestic policies within the framework of the international agreements reached in the field of combating drug trafficking [3].

Among the states that are most loyal to illicit consumption and related drug trafficking are Holland, Italy, Spain, Switzerland and Germany. However, it is worth noting that the legislation of these countries differentiates the types of liability depending on the type of drug.

They are characterized by fairly severe punishment for the manufacture and distribution of drugs such as LSD, heroin, cocaine, opium, and less severe punishment for marijuana, hashish, etc. The characteristic features of the German Criminal Code are the principles of legality, establishing the punishability of only those acts that were prohibited by law until they were committed.

The German Criminal Code reflects the main provisions of the classical school of criminal law on free will, forms and types of guilt, the interdependence of personal freedom and responsibility, as well as the concept of retribution [4].

Let us note that the system of sources of criminal law in Germany consists of the Basic Law of the Federal Republic of Germany, the Criminal Code of the Federal Republic of Germany of 1871 (as amended on March 10, 1987) and other criminal laws.

Germany, due to its convenient location, is what is called a “tidbit” for drug traffickers, and this country attracts them not only as a market for the sale of prohibited goods, but also as an opportunity for its further distribution throughout Europe. In Germany, all drugs are classified into 3 main groups.

The first and most dangerous group includes cocaine, heroin, methadone, ecstasy, opium and LSD. The second group is dangerous drugs, which include all major types and varieties of amphetamines, as well as cannabis and codeine. And the third group is the least dangerous drugs, such as benzodiazepines, some amphetamines and sedatives.

Germany is one of the countries with so-called “consumers” of narcotic drugs, and the specificity of the criminal law of this state is that the criminal law rules establishing liability for illegal drug trafficking are not contained in the Special Part of the Criminal Code (Criminal Code) of Germany [5, 6], and in the Law on Drug Trafficking of July 28, 1981 (as amended and supplemented), which relates to the so-called additional criminal law.

The salient features of the Narcotic Drugs Act 1981 are:

1) an expanded list of acts related to illicit drug trafficking that have become recognized as criminal;

2) the amount of punishment for serious crimes in the field of illicit drug trafficking has increased. This provision is a consequence of increased criminal liability for actions related to illicit drug trafficking committed by organized criminal groups;

3) an expanded list of acts related to illegal drug trafficking, when the court hearing the case of illegal drug trafficking may reduce the punishment or refuse it;

4) implementation of the principle of “therapy instead of punishment”, i.e. the penal authorities are given the opportunity, with the consent of the court, instead of executing a sentence of imprisonment for a term of no more than two years in cases involving the conviction of persons with drug addiction, for the rehabilitation of such a person assign him placement in a special medical and therapeutic institution.

However, this is allowed only in cases where it is clearly established that the crime was committed by a person due to his drug addiction.

However, in practice, the application of this norm often causes certain difficulties, and this is due, first of all, to the fact that in the German penal system there is not a sufficient number of special treatment and therapeutic institutions to accommodate persons suffering from drug addiction and who have committed a crime in connection with this.

All this leads to the fact that persons wishing to undergo treatment are placed in such medical institutions untimely or cannot be placed at all due to the lack of a sufficient number of such institutions.

In March 2000, the legislator made appropriate changes, which provided for "... the possibility of creating special institutions at the level of federal states where persons suffering from drug addiction could stay for a certain period of time required for healing" [7].

At the same time, while staying in these institutions, under certain conditions, the use of narcotic drugs is allowed. It is worth paying attention to the fact that most of the drugs that are considered illegal today were used in medicine as medicines back in the last century.

So, in the middle of the 20th century, opiates (morphine, codeine, papaverine, thebaine, tincture of opium, omnopon, etc.) were used in Germany to treat alcoholism [8].

Currently, drugs of the opium group are used:

- as central analgesics for pain of various origins (injuries accompanied by significant pain; inflammatory processes in internal organs, etc.);
- as sleeping pills for insomnia due to severe pain;
- to reduce the excitability of the cough center during persistent cough, especially dry cough, etc.

When prescribing opium drugs, one should take into account the possibility of developing tolerance to them (a reduced reaction of the body to repeated use of the substance) and addiction (an irresistible painful desire to re-take the drug) - opium addiction.

Thus, according to members of the UN Global Commission, drug legalization can be a more effective way to combat them than harsh penalties and criminal prosecution of drug addicts.

Kofi Annan (former UN Secretary General) and the ex-presidents of Colombia, Brazil and Mexico came to this conclusion, explaining that the accumulated experience in the fight against the spread and use of drugs shows that radical measures only lead to increased crime, an increase in drug trafficking, and more spread and worsening of the general situation.

The legalization of certain types of drugs will have the opposite effect and will make it possible to get rid of drug crime by avoiding violent and coercive methods.

In 2006, an experiment was conducted in Germany: on the streets of some cities, with the permission of the government, mobile laboratories offered people who illegally consume drugs to take them on a legal basis, with a document confirming drug addiction. Even heroin injections were offered.

According to the police, during the experiment (from September 2006 to January 2007), on the one hand, the number of crimes related to the illegal acquisition of drugs (theft of drugs) significantly decreased, and on the other hand, there was a sharp increase in the number of crimes committed by persons illegally consuming drugs under their influence and negative reaction to the experiment from the public.

In September 2014, the Global Commission on Drug Policy presented its report on the global drug trafficking situation in New York and called it "revolutionary."

Members of the Commission proposed legalizing the use and possession of all drugs, except crack cocaine and desomorphine, stopping the prosecution of small drug dealers, and regulating the sale of drugs using the same mechanisms as tobacco products and alcoholic beverages.

The authors of the report entitled it "Taking Control: Towards Effective Drug Policy" and generally avoid using the word "legalization", preferring the expression "state control" [9].

However, in essence we are talking about the decriminalization of drug trafficking and the transition to legal regulation of psychoactive substances.

One of the members of the Drug Policy Commission, Richard Branson, stated that "... We cannot continue to pretend that the war on drugs is producing any positive results...The risks associated with substance use increase - sometimes catastrophically - when they are produced, sold and used in unregulated, criminal conditions.

The most effective way to protect public health and safety is to bring drugs under control through responsible legal regulation." However, in our opinion, it is worth disagreeing with this statement, since the legalization of drugs is categorically unacceptable and can lead to a general drug addiction in society.

If we consider the experience of legalizing "soft" drugs in the USA and the Netherlands, then we can confidently say that this has not led to anything positive - over the past 10 years in the USA, the number of deaths from overdose has increased 3 times [10].

It should also be noted that marijuana use inevitably leads to psychiatric diseases - schizophrenia and deep depression - and in the future, as a rule, leads to the use of more "hard" drugs.

Changes and additions have been repeatedly made to German criminal legislation regarding the extent of punishment for illegal transactions with narcotic drugs.

In particular, possession of drugs is punishable by imprisonment for a term of 1 to 4 years or a fine, and for possession of drugs in large quantities - imprisonment from 1 to 15 years.

Thus, an analysis of the legal regulation of combating drug trafficking shows that the system of influences and punishment of the anti-drug legislation of Germany is specific, and this is due not only to the national characteristics of the country, but also to the crime situation in this area.

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